

ISic3427

I.Sicily inscription 3427

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

from foundation works for the post office, between via Eumelo, via Archia, and via Carabelli

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 644822

Bibliography

Gentili, G.V. 1961. Nuovi elementi di epigrafia siracusana. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 7: 5-25. At 7-8 no.2 dr

Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 186 no.1 tav.64

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